

COVID-19 APPROACHES ON CORPORATE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY

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Abstract

Purpose - The purpose of this research is to identify how Romanian organizations have implemented corporate social responsibility models by examining employees' perceptions of the relationship between management behavior and actions and employee morale.

Methodology/approach – Qualitative research based on case studies with used semi-structured interviews. The study contains data from 10 respondents from 7 companies and compiles enough information to understand the investigated phenomenon.

Findings - The labor market impediments created by the Covid-19 pandemic, requires the update of the company's policies for permanent or remote employees, flexible employees and / or mixed location, but also for new employees.

Research limitations/implications - the impossibility of extrapolating the results to the entire researched population. One of the limits of qualitative research is that only SMEs from Bucharest, Brașov, Cluj, Galați, Prahova are considered. Thus, the results are relatively particular and difficult to generalize.

Practical implications - Most respondents agree that human resource management is one of the internal dimensions of corporate social responsibility.

Originality/value - The contribution of this study is remarkable, as it explores the impact of the pandemic on the staff recruitment and selection process, but also on employee retention.

Key words - CSR, talent management, post-pandemic actions

Introduction

In recent years, corporate social responsibility has become an increasingly hot topic in the academic community because of business activities on employees, customers, authorities, society, business partners, investors, the environment, and local communities. In this regard, a growing number of companies are pursuing, through sustained efforts, the inclusion of corporate social responsibility practices in their business strategies.

Literature review

Howard Bowen, also considered the father of corporate social responsibility, put forward practically the first definition of corporate social responsibility: "the obligations of businesspeople to follow those policies, to make those decisions, or to follow those directions that are agreed in terms of values and objectives by our society" (Bowen, 1953).

In 2011, with the publication of the new European Strategy 2011-2014 on Corporate Social Responsibility, the European Commission published a new definition: "the responsibility of companies for the impact they have on society" (European Commission, 2011).

The following reasons appear to be the main reasons why companies choose to implement corporate social responsibility activities:

- environmental issues (Murphy & Bendell, 1997);

- increasing the expectations of customers and employees, legislation and pressures exerted by state authorities, investor's interest in social criteria and changing purchasing practices of economic agents (Bögel, 2015);
- strategic or even defensive, altruistic or public-oriented motives (Vogel, 2005);
- "civil regulations", social responsibility - "the tribute that capitalism pays, everywhere, for virtue" (Vogel, 2005);
- improving conditions; inducing economic growth by leading the company in such a way as to respect the environment, human rights; obtaining a competitive position; a high degree of employee morality or a better reputation; redirection of discretionary resources; profitability (Vogel, 2005);
- the fiscal benefits, the increase of the company's visibility, the consumers' preference for the products of the socially responsible companies, the increase of the internal cohesion of the team involved in the development of the project within the respective company, etc. (Vogel, 2005);
- creating value, thus gaining legitimacy, maintaining its status and maximizing its long-term economic efficiency (Vogel, 2005);
- altruism, this being the first reason why social responsibility appeared in America around the 1980s (Bueble, 2008);
- compliance with the law, ethical conduct, as well as the adoption of a responsible behavior that proves that there is that social consciousness characteristic of the corporate citizen (Kotler & Keller, 2008);

CSR practices improve the standard of living of society (Jamali, 2008), contribute to economic development (Chapple & Moon, 2005), address social and environmental issues such as human rights, environmental pollution and environmental problems and the workplace that employees struggle with (Dumitrescu, Simionescu, & Roman, 2015). Some gaps in research on the implementation of CSR practices have been identified in the literature (Dumitrescu & Simionescu, 2014). Thus, the various CSR practices that include the culture and traditional customs of developed countries are not applicable in developing countries such as Romania.

Following a study conducted in 2012 by a group of Romanian researchers, the following conclusions were reached: first, the vast majority of company managers did not understand what it means to be a socially responsible company, which is why I do not even agree with most of the definitions given to corporate social responsibility; secondly, when asked to explain what social responsibility means, they were not able to make logical arguments; they argued that the involvement of companies in social responsibility activities has a purely economic motivation and that it is related to the size of the company, rather large companies integrating the implementation of CSR activities in its vision (Herman, Georgescu, & Georgescu, 2012).

Purpose of the study

The year 2020 was a transformational year. The pandemic has highlighted the ability as individuals, companies, governments to adapt and change. The unprecedented health crisis has led to the need to consider that social issues, such as employee safety and especially their well-being may be in the interest of the company, even in the absence of direct economic benefits, or costs.

Attracting and retaining creative people in the organization, able to make decisions and focus on problem solving, is one of the biggest challenges for company leaders today, so ensuring a positive work experience for employees is essential.

Business leaders around the world have learned valuable lessons as they have sacrificed short-term profit for long-term resilience, rapidly changing traditional strategies to ensure their current survival and future prosperity, but also to retain and train employees.

An employee's experience includes everything he encounters in his daily activities, observes, and feels within the company he belongs to, beyond his involvement in the role of employee and organizational culture. The last two years have managed to change the way companies perceive this experience, especially since it does not refer, as many companies considered, only to occasional bonuses or appreciations, but throughout the existence of an employee in the company - from attracting and recruitment, onboarding, development, and retention. Another characteristic of contemporary society is

the assumption that at work, in performing the daily tasks, each employee behaves in a conscious and responsible manner. Being a good citizen now means appreciating values, behaving responsibly and morally, helping to maintain a clean environment, and having decent interpersonal relationships, requirements that apply to companies, but also to their employees.

The purpose of this research is to identify how Romanian organizations have implemented corporate social responsibility models by examining employee's perceptions of the relationship between management behavior and actions and employee morale.

Methodology

The research is qualitative based on case studies in which we used semi-structured interviews to collect data from respondents. The study contains data from 10 respondents (managers and above positions) from 7 companies and compiles enough information to understand the investigated phenomenon.

Findings and results

The experience on management position of the 10 respondents (70% men and 30% women, aged 35-60 years, 40% with bachelor's degree and 60% with master's degree) differs from 1-2 years to over 20. From their answers we could see that they are involved not only in the core business, but also in that of subordinate employees, but even in other departments, supporting them, giving them suggestions, informing employees about the possibilities of updating their knowledge and skills, taking the initiative to discuss things if they have departmental or inter-departmental problems. Based on the interviews, we found, among other things, the labor market impediments created by the Covid-19 pandemic, which require to update the company's policies for permanent or remote employees, flexible employees and / or mixed location, but also for new employees.

Most respondents agree that human resource management is one of the internal dimensions of corporate social responsibility. They agree that corporate social responsibility must include measures of transparency and good information throughout the company, a sustainable and general balance between objectives or work tasks and personal and / or family needs, equal pay and career opportunities, active promotion of employees in a situation of inactivity due to permanent / temporary illnesses / disabilities, but also with the fact that the company must develop measures for employees by providing equal treatment, a sustainable and equitable structure.

A few actions that were taken during the pandemic by the management of the 7 companies, included:

1. Giving masks to employees (1 box with 50 pieces per month), disinfectants, gloves where necessary
2. Postponement of shift entry / exit hours
3. Visual training by displaying posters and banners
4. Disinfection action by nebulization
5. Telework (where applicable)
6. Online meetings and conferences
7. Giving a package of protective food once a month

Post-pandemic actions no. 5 to 7 are still maintained, and steps are taken to implement measures for new employees, namely: online orientation trainings and video information materials.

For all employees, the management is aware that they must hire the right person in the right role, which is a human resource priority. Thus, one goal is to prepare a multi-qualification matrix by cross-training people and exposing them to different parts of the business.

Also, for to streamline the processes and the revision of the company's structures, a system for evaluating the potential of the employees is being implemented, together with a succession plan from which are emerging the training needs. The potential is between a person's current abilities and possible future roles, considering the person's ability to grow and long-term derailments. Talent refers to the

natural ability to excel in debt or in performing an action. Talent management refers to a critical process that ensures the company the quantity and quality of people to meet current and future business priorities. Skills are observable and measurable characteristics of a person related to success in the workplace.

Succession plans help identify potential candidates for existing positions, considering the needs of the company and the objectives, competencies, and development potential of the candidates. Potential candidates could be approached in terms of their interest in succession possibilities. Stakeholders could then be developed for future roles and responsibilities and, where appropriate, could benefit from the opportunity to hold multiple management positions during periods of temporary absence of employees from those positions.

Most of the managers interviewed stated that another measure for employee loyalty and retention is the implementation of a system for rewarding suggestions for improvement and innovation.

Discussion and conclusions

The contribution of this study is remarkable, as it explores the impact of the pandemic on the staff recruitment and selection process, but also on employee retention.

We have made some suggestions for adapting to the new changes for effective work:

- The psycho-emotional health of employees, a priority through the implementation of a culture of hygiene and integrated health.
- Hiring Romanian citizens: attracting and supporting talents by creating conditions for inclusion and integration, meaning processes and tools for a digital onboarding to face the permanent challenges of being able to retain valuable employees in the company.
- Adaptation to technological needs, imposed by remote and hybrid work - by constantly adapting to legal requirements, this process also comes with a planning of investments in high-performance IT equipment and services.

Talent management is also quite new to Romanian HR practices. Its purpose is to determine the necessary competence for the personnel carrying out activities that influence the compliance with the requirements regarding the product / environment / OHS performance by evaluating the effectiveness of the actions undertaken and to set the methodology for identifying training needs to ensure that personnel performing activities that influence product quality are adequate based on appropriate education, training and / or experience, as required.

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